

AI-Based Non-destructive Surface Roughness Detection for Stainless Steel using Thermal Imaging

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Abstract: Surface roughness is a critical parameter in quality control for precision manufacturing, especially for stainless steel components used in the food and pharmaceutical industries where hygienic surface standards are required. Conventional contact-based measurement techniques provide high accuracy but are time-consuming and unsuitable for real-time industrial inspection. This research proposes an AI-based non-destructive surface roughness detection method for stainless steel using thermal imaging. Active Infrared Thermography was employed to capture thermal reflection patterns from stainless steel surfaces with different roughness conditions. The acquired thermal images were processed using a deep learning model based on YOLOv11 to classify surface roughness characteristics. Stainless steel specimens were prepared using different polishing conditions, including 40, 80, 180, and 400 mesh sandpapers, as well as Scotch-Brite surface finishing. Experimental results demonstrated that the proposed system could effectively distinguish surface conditions with classification accuracies ranging from 85% to 100%. The findings indicate that thermal imaging combined with artificial intelligence has strong potential for rapid, non-contact, and non-destructive surface inspection in industrial manufacturing applications.

Keywords: Infrared thermal imaging, YOLOv11, Deep learning, Surface roughness

1. INTRODUCTION

Surface roughness is an important factor affecting the quality, performance, and service life of industrial products, especially in manufacturing engineering applications. Surface characteristics are closely related to friction, wear resistance, and assembly performance of mechanical components. Furthermore, in industries requiring strict hygienic standards, such as the food and pharmaceutical industries [1][2], surface smoothness plays a critical role in preventing contamination and microbial accumulation on equipment surfaces. Therefore, the inspection and evaluation of surface roughness are essential steps in industrial quality control processes to maintain manufacturing standards and product safety.

Conventionally, surface roughness measurement in industrial applications is commonly performed using contact-type roughness measurement instruments or profilometers [3]. These devices operate using a stylus probe moving across the workpiece surface to record the surface profile, from which roughness parameters such as Ra and Rz are calculated [4]. However, such methods have several limitations, including direct physical contact with the surface, time-consuming measurement procedures, and unsuitability for continuous production-line inspection or non-destructive testing applications [5]. Consequently, there is a growing interest in developing non-contact measurement techniques as alternative methods for surface evaluation.

To overcome these limitations, this research proposes a non-contact and non-destructive testing (NDT) approach using Active Infrared Thermography for evaluating the surface roughness characteristics of stainless-steel materials [6]. The method relies on analyzing the temperature distribution patterns obtained from thermal images of the specimen surfaces [7]. The acquired thermal images were processed using image processing techniques combined with deep learning based on the YOLOv11 convolutional neural network model to analyze surface characteristics and classify different roughness levels [8]. The results demonstrate the potential of this approach for non-contact surface roughness estimation and industrial quality inspection applications.

Our research objectives are as follows:

1. To investigate the relationship between thermal image characteristics and stainless-steel surface roughness levels using Active Infrared Thermography.
2. To develop a stainless-steel surface roughness estimation method using thermal imaging combined with image processing and YOLOv11 deep learning techniques.
3. To demonstrate the potential of a non-contact thermal imaging system for stainless steel surface roughness inspection toward future industrial applications.

2. Research Methodology

2.1 Preparation of Stainless-Steel Surface Samples

In this study, stainless steel specimens were prepared to investigate the relationship between surface characteristics and thermal imaging patterns. AISI 304 stainless steel was selected because it is widely used in food, pharmaceutical, and industrial machinery applications due to its corrosion resistance, mechanical strength, and good formability. Moreover, it is commonly applied in hygienic equipment requiring clean and smooth surfaces.

The stainless-steel samples were prepared with different surface conditions using polishing processes to simulate real industrial surface characteristics. Sandpapers with different grit sizes, including 40 mesh, 80 mesh, 180 mesh, and 400 mesh, were used. In addition, Scotch-Brite finishing was applied to create various surface textures representative of polishing, grinding, and machining processes as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Stainless-steel plates with surface roughness levels of 40 MESH, 80 MESH, and 180 MESH.

2.2 Surface Roughness Measurement using a Profilometer

The surface roughness value of the stainless-steel specimens was measured using a profilometer, which is a standard instrument for evaluating surface texture characteristics [3]. The profilometer operates by moving a stylus probe along the sample surface to detect height variations and convert the measurements into quantitative surface roughness values [4]. The measured roughness values were used as reference standards for comparison with the thermal image analysis results as shown in figure 2.

The results indicate that the average surface roughness values varied according to the abrasive grit size as shown table 1. The 40 mesh surface exhibited the highest roughness value of 1.9898 μm , while the 400 mesh surface showed the lowest value of 0.2593 μm . Surfaces treated with Scotch-Brite exhibited intermediate roughness levels.

Figure 2. Measurement of Ra values using a profilometer.

Table 1. Results of Ra value measurements.

Surface type	Ra (μm)
40 MESH	1.9898
80 MESH	0.884033
180 MESH	0.797733
400 MESH	0.2593
180 MESH + Scotch Brite	0.558467
320 MESH + Scotch Brite	0.38937

2.3 Thermal Imaging Acquisition of Stainless-Steel Surfaces

A FLIR A315 infrared thermal camera was used to capture thermal images of the stainless-steel surfaces. The camera employs an uncooled microbolometer sensor capable of detecting infrared radiation within the wavelength range of 7.5–13 μm , with a detector resolution of 320×240 pixels and NETD < 50 mK. The camera transmitted 16-bit thermal image data through a GigE interface at 60 Hz [9].

The camera was positioned approximately 60 cm away from the specimen under room temperature conditions of approximately 27°C. A calibrated infrared blackbody source (Fluke 4180 Infrared calibrator) was used as a thermal excitation source for Active Thermography. The reflected infrared radiation from the specimen surface represented the thermal distribution characteristics associated with the surface roughness condition [10].

Figure 3. Experimental setup and methodology.

As shown in Figures 3 and 4, the acquired thermal images were further analyzed and processed using image processing and artificial intelligence techniques to investigate their relationship with the surface characteristics of stainless steel. The thermal images demonstrated clear differences in temperature distribution patterns among surfaces polished with different grit sizes. Rough surfaces such as 40 mesh exhibited non-uniform thermal distribution patterns, while smoother surfaces such as 400 mesh showed more uniform temperature distributions.

Figure 4. Thermal image acquisition results.

2.4 Relationship between Emissivity and Thermal Imaging

The relationship between thermal imaging and emissivity (ε) is based on the principle that all objects emit thermal radiation in the form of infrared energy. Thermal cameras detect this radiation and convert it into temperature information. The emissivity value represents the ratio between the thermal radiation emitted by a real object and that emitted by an ideal blackbody at the same temperature.

$$E = \varepsilon\sigma T^4 \quad (1)$$

where E is the thermal radiation emitted from the object surface (W/m^2), ε is the emissivity, σ is the Stefan–Boltzmann constant, and T is the absolute temperature in Kelvin [7]. This equation indicates that the emitted thermal radiation depends on both temperature and material emissivity.

In practical thermal imaging applications, the detected radiation is affected not only by object emission but also by reflected environmental radiation and atmospheric radiation. Therefore, the total radiance captured by the thermal camera can be described using the radiance model as in equation 2.

$$L_{cam} = \tau[\varepsilon L(T_{obj}) + (1 - \varepsilon)L(T_{refl})] + (1 - \tau)L(T_{atm}) \quad (2)$$

Where L_{cam} represents the total radiative energy detected by the camera from the object surface, consisting of the emitted radiation from the object $L(T_{obj})$, the reflected environmental radiation $L(T_{refl})$ and the atmospheric radiation $L(T_{atm})$. Meanwhile, τ denotes the atmospheric transmissivity, representing the fraction of radiative energy that can propagate through the atmosphere to the camera detector.

Under real operating conditions, environmental variations such as fluctuating ambient temperatures, nearby heat sources, or changes in air humidity can significantly affect the reflected radiation $L(T_{refl})$ and atmospheric radiation $L(T_{atm})$. These effects may introduce errors in the total radiative energy detected by the camera, leading to reduced accuracy in object temperature calculations. This issue becomes particularly critical for low-emissivity materials, such as polished metals, which tend to strongly reflect surrounding environmental radiation.

The above equation demonstrates that the emissivity of a material surface plays a crucial role in the accuracy of temperature measurements obtained from thermal imaging, as it directly influences the calculation of object temperature from the radiative energy detected by the camera [10].

2.5 Dataset Preparation and Image Processing

In this research, the thermal images obtained from the experiments were used as input data for the development of an artificial intelligence model. The dataset was prepared and managed using the Roboflow platform, which is a tool designed for computer vision dataset management and preprocessing. The platform supports image importation, data annotation, and image enhancement to ensure suitability for training deep learning-based object detection models.

During the data preparation process, the thermal images acquired from the experiments were uploaded into the Roboflow system. Bounding boxes were then assigned to the target regions on each image to serve as labels for model training. In addition, all images were resized to a standard resolution of 512×512 pixels to optimize compatibility with the artificial intelligence model and reduce computational complexity.

After the data preparation stage, the complete dataset consisting of 622 thermal images was divided into two subsets: 560 images (90%) for the training set and 62 images (10%) for the validation set. No separate test set was allocated at this stage. The purpose of this dataset partitioning was to train the model and evaluate its performance in learning the characteristics of thermal image data.

The dataset preparation and preprocessing procedures play a significant role in the overall performance of the model, as the quality and suitability of the dataset directly affect the model's ability to learn and detect important features from thermal images. This contributes to improving the accuracy of image detection and classification in subsequent processing stages, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Data augmentation process in Roboflow.

2.6 YOLOv11 Algorithm

YOLO (You Only Look Once) is an object detection algorithm that utilizes deep neural networks to detect and classify objects from images within a single processing stage. This enables rapid object detection and makes the model suitable for real-time processing applications [11].

The working principle of YOLO involves dividing an image into grids, after which the model predicts the locations of objects in the form of bounding boxes while simultaneously identifying the object classes and confidence scores within a single processing step [11].

Previous studies have shown that YOLO models have been widely applied in various fields, such as contamination inspection in packaging processes and classification of contaminants including water, oil, grease, and cleaning agents, by learning the unique characteristics of thermal profiles obtained from thermal imaging [12].

Furthermore, the integration of thermal imaging techniques with YOLO models has demonstrated promising performance in the food industry. For example, the application of YOLOv8 for broiler disease detection achieved high accuracy, with an mAP50 value of 0.988, while automated counting applications reported mAP values as high as 95% [13].

In addition, deep learning-based object detection techniques have been applied in spoiled food inspection, abnormal fish detection in aquaculture systems, and surface defect inspection in industrial applications [14]. YOLOv11 is an advanced version developed by Ultralytics as a continuation of YOLOv8 and previous YOLO versions. The network architecture has been further optimized to improve detection accuracy and computational efficiency for practical applications, including industrial quality inspection, medical image analysis, and real-time object detection systems. In this study, the YOLO model was employed to learn and process thermal images to classify the surface characteristics of stainless-steel materials.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 YOLOv11 Training Results

The training results of the YOLOv11 model over 100 epochs demonstrated that the training process utilized a dataset consisting of 560 samples, with a nearly balanced number of samples in each class. This enabled the model to effectively learn the surface characteristics at different roughness levels.

In addition, the model achieved a high performance, with an mAP@0.5 value of approximately 0.995 and an mAP@0.5:0.95 value of approximately 0.89. At the same time, the precision and recall values gradually increased and approached 1.0 toward the end of the training process, indicating that the model was able to accurately detect and classify objects, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Training results of the YOLOv11.

The training loss and validation loss showed a continuous decreasing trend, indicating that the model was able to effectively learn the characteristics of the dataset, as shown in Figures 7 and 8.

Figure 7. Training results showing the training loss.

Figure 8. Training results showing the validation loss.

The Precision–Recall graph obtained from the testing results showed that all classes achieved high Average Precision values. The model attained an mAP@0.5 value of

approximately 0.995, indicating that it could detect and classify objects with high efficiency, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Precision–Recall curve of the model.

The F1–Confidence curve showed that the maximum F1 score was approximately 1.0 at a confidence threshold of around 0.82, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Training results of the YOLOv11.

The Confusion Matrix results showed that the model was able to accurately classify the surface roughness classes without misclassification between classes. This indicates that the model could effectively distinguish the surface characteristics at each roughness level, as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Confusion matrix of the results.

3.2 Thermal Imaging Test Results of Stainless-Steel Surfaces

In this experiment, real-time thermal images of the stainless-steel surfaces were captured using a FLIR A315 thermal imaging camera. The camera was mounted on a tripod to maintain a constant position throughout the experiment. The distance between the camera and the workpiece was set at approximately 60 centimeters to ensure clear and comprehensive image coverage of the entire sample surface.

The experiment was conducted under room temperature conditions of approximately 27°C, with the environment strictly controlled during each imaging session to minimize external factors that could affect the measured thermal data. Subsequently, 20 thermal images were recorded for each type of stainless-steel surface sample. This dataset was used to evaluate the efficiency of the model in classifying the surface roughness levels of the stainless steel. The resulting test data are summarized and presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Surface Roughness Classification Results

Surface Type	Ra (μm)	Total Samples	Pass	Not Pass	Accuracy (%)
40 Mesh	1.98	20	18	2	90
80 Mesh	0.88	20	17	3	85
180 Mesh	0.79	20	0	20	0
400 Mesh	0.25	20	18	2	90
180 Mesh + Scotch-Brite	0.55	20	20	0	100
320 Mesh + Scotch-Brite	0.38	20	20	0	100

Table 2 presents the classification results of the stainless-steel surfaces obtained from the thermal images. Based on 20 sample images per surface type, the model demonstrated effective classification capabilities across various surface roughness levels. The 40 Mesh (Ra = 1.98 μm) and 400 Mesh (Ra = 0.25 μm) surfaces achieved an accuracy rate of 90%, while the 80 Mesh (Ra = 0.88 μm) surface yielded an accuracy rate of 85%.

Furthermore, the surfaces that underwent additional polishing with Scotch-Brite—specifically 180 Mesh + Scotch-Brite (Ra = 0.55 μm) and 320 Mesh + Scotch-Brite (Ra = 0.38 μm)—were classified with absolute correctness, representing 100% accuracy.

However, the 180 Mesh (Ra = 0.79 μm) surface resulted in an accuracy rate of 0%. This was due to its roughness being close to that of the 80 Mesh (Ra = 0.88 μm) surface. Consequently, the temperature distribution patterns on the thermal images were nearly identical, causing the model to fail to clearly distinguish between these two surface conditions.

Figure 10. Object detection results and surface roughness values obtained from the YOLO model.

The experimental results showed that the model could classify stainless steel surface conditions effectively. The 40 mesh and 400 mesh surfaces achieved classification accuracies of 90%, while the 80 mesh surface achieved 85% accuracy. Surfaces treated with Scotch-Brite achieved 100% classification accuracy.

However, the 180 mesh surface achieved 0% accuracy because its roughness value was very close to that of the 80 mesh surface, resulting in similar thermal distribution patterns that the model could not clearly distinguish.

The YOLO model successfully detected surface regions and estimated roughness values based on thermal image characteristics. Rougher surfaces exhibited more irregular thermal distributions compared to smoother surfaces.

4. Conclusion

This research investigated a non-contact stainless steel surface roughness estimation method using infrared thermal imaging combined with deep learning techniques. Thermal images of stainless-steel specimens with different polishing conditions were captured using a FLIR A315 thermal camera, and YOLOv11 was used for surface classification. The training results demonstrated high model performance, achieving an mAP@0.5 value of approximately 0.995 and an mAP@0.5:0.95 value of approximately 0.89 after 100 epochs.

Experimental testing showed that the model achieved 90% accuracy for 40 mesh and 400 mesh surfaces, 85% accuracy for 80 mesh surfaces, and 100% accuracy for Scotch-Brite treated surfaces. However, the classification accuracy for the 180 mesh surface was low due to the similarity of its thermal image characteristics to those of the 80 mesh surface. In conclusion, the integration of thermal imaging and deep learning techniques provides an effective non-contact method for stainless steel surface roughness estimation and demonstrates strong potential for industrial quality inspection applications.

Future work should focus on increasing the dataset size and improving model training strategies to enhance classification performance for surfaces with similar roughness characteristics.

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